

World Safety Journal

A peer-reviewed journal,
published by the World Safety Organization

Journal Homepage:
<https://worldsafety.org/wso-world-safety-journal/>

Analysis of Australian Coronial Inquest and Non-Inquest findings of heavy vehicle fatal crashes reveals shortcomings in investigations!

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KEYWORDS

Heavy Vehicle
Train
Investigation
Level Crossing
Crash
Human Factors

ABSTRACT

Heavy vehicle crashes occur daily where drivers, occupants and other road users are either killed or seriously injured. Investigations are conducted by regulatory authorities of these crashes and reports are submitted to the Coroner to determine the cause of death, make findings regarding the cause of the crash and then make recommendations to improve safety and mitigate the risk of a crash occurring. The Coroner plays a critical role in examining the cause of these crashes; however, this research has identified there are a number of substandard investigative practices where the investigations have not obtained the level of detail that would assist the Coroner in making appropriate findings. This study has also identified that this sub-optimal practice has been ongoing for a considerable period of time with a number of Coroners expressing their concerns. This study has reviewed a total of 34 publicly available Coronial Inquest and Non-Inquest findings. The review has identified there are inconsistencies in the quality of the investigations. A fatal crash investigation properly conducted can be a valuable tool in identify why a crash has occurred and greatly assist the Coroner the opportunity to make recommendations from the findings to improve heavy vehicle transport safety.

1. INTRODUCTION

Coroners plays a critical role in examining the underlying causes of the deaths and have the opportunity to make recommendations from findings to improve safety (Brodie et al., 2010). Coroners however rely on the information presented to them from the fatal crash investigation report or from the information presented during an Inquest if one is held. The quality of that investigation or the Inquest is dependent on the experiences, competencies and knowledge of the investigator and the type of investigative methodology being used, if any (Cikara et al., 2020).

A fatal crash investigation, properly conducted, can be a valuable tool in identifying the underlying causes and contributory factors of a crash, why a crash has occurred and suggesting recommendations for future prevention (Brodie et al., 2010; Klockner & Toft, 2014; Dell, 2015; Dell, 2019). In most instances the heavy vehicle fatal crash investigation is conducted on behalf of Coroners by the police. As stated by various Coroners, police may not have the knowledge, skills, competencies and resources

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to understand and navigate the complexities of the heavy vehicle transport industry socio-technical system and in some instances do not know what is needed to investigate a heavy vehicle crash to identify the underlying causes (Productivity Commission, 2020).

The role of police is diverse, as well as complex, with competing priorities. In most instances police investigate matters for prosecution purposes or for identifying liability (Selk & Benner, 2019; Doecke et al., 2020; Productivity Commission, 2020) and their investigative training is not specific to the heavy vehicle transport industry (Productivity Commission, 2020), with most investigators either learning their skills on the job or bringing those skills acquired elsewhere with them which may not be conducive to the regulatory setting they are working within.

2. CORONERS

A Coroner's primary role is to establish the cause and circumstances of a sudden or unexplained death. The role of a Coroner is fact finding, inquisitorial rather than fault finding, adversarial (Burns, 2014). Deputy Coroner Loch of the Office of the State Coroner Queensland (2014) in a Finding of Inquest (File 2012/334) stated *'An Inquest is not a trial between opposing parties but an inquiry into the death. The focus is on discovering what happened, not on ascribing guilt, attributing blame or apportioning liability'* (p. 2). Chief Justice Neal Maclean described New Zealand's coronial process as speaking *'truth to power'* and the New Zealand Coroners website explains that a *'Coroner speaks for the dead to protect the living'* (Burns, 2014). The Western Australian State Coroner has stated that: *'It is said that the role of the Coroner's Court is to speak for the dead and to protect the living. This two-fold role is a vital component of a civil society'* (Fogliani, 2017, p. 5).

Information drawn from a Coronial Inquest is vital to facilitate risk identification and strengthen countermeasures (Brodie et al., 2009). The significance of Coroners' recommendations and comments is their ability to advocate for change and potential wide-ranging impact (Brodie et al., 2010). In a study to quantify Coroners' recommendations and examine the nature of those recommendations according to public health principles of injury causation and prevention, Bugeja et al. (2012) stated that *'exploring the characteristics of recommendations generated from medicolegal death investigations is an important step towards improving their contribution to injury prevention'* (p. 326).

Throughout Australia, Coroners' courts are state based jurisdictions where it is a legislated requirement that all deaths, including heavy vehicle fatal crashes must be reported to the Coroner in the State or Territory in which that fatal crash occurs. Generally speaking, any unexpected, unnatural or violent death must be reported. Internationally, within the Commonwealth, the requirement is not too dissimilar. In fact, throughout the United Kingdom and countries of the British Commonwealth there is much in common (Studdert & Cordner, 2010).

Coroners undertake Inquests based on the information gathered by police during the investigative process. Studdert and Cordner (2010) identified that a Coroner's role in establishing cause of deaths is especially valuable for fatalities in which the fundamental cause is obscure, or first impressions are misleading, which can be the case in heavy vehicle crashes. However, it was found that Coroners have limited resources where accurately identifying causes of deaths requires prudent efforts and directions towards investigations (Studdert & Cordner, 2010). Studdert and Cordner (2010) identified that coronial investigations in Australia changed basic presumptions about how deaths occur only in a small number of cases. This is concerning considering the findings of previous research that expressed concerns at the lack of quality of investigations of heavy vehicle crash fatalities (Victorian Parliament Law Reform Committee Review, 2006; Brodie et al., 2009; Brodie et al., 2010). This is made even more complicated where there has been a continuous effort to apportion blame for crashes on those directly involved such as the driver of a vehicle and then taking legal action against them (Dell, 2015).

3. AIM

The aim of this research project was to analyse the findings of Coronial Inquests and Non-Inquests to identify whether investigations of heavy vehicle fatal crashes by police provided sufficient evidence of crash causation for Coroners to make informed decisions and recommendations to improve safety in the heavy vehicle transport industry.

4. METHOD

A search was conducted of each Australian State and Territory-based Coroner's office website. Publicly available coronial reports were searched to identify those reports that included a crash involving a heavy vehicle. The search was conducted for the years between 2005 and 2020. The reports were either those arising from an Inquest as well as findings from a Non-Inquest. In total 34 reports were selected. Each report was downloaded and read to ensure the report fell within the date range and included a crash involving a heavy vehicle. The reports selected came from the Coroners Courts in the states of New South Wales, Tasmanian, Victorian, South Australian, Queensland and Western Australian.

The analysis identified the type of crash, i.e., truck vs car, the type of report, i.e., Inquest or Non-Inquest, the findings and recommendations, the number of recommendations and types of recommendations. The reports were further analysed to identify:

- If the crash was considered a workplace crash or not;
- The type of investigative methodology used by investigators;
- If comments were made by the Coroner with regards to the quality of the investigation and information provided;
- Who was involved in the investigation process i.e., Police, Worksafe, National Heavy Vehicle Regulator, Office of Transport Safety Investigations, Office National Rail Safety Regulator or others.

5. CRASH TYPE

The search results identified 34 Coroners reports comprising of 13 x truck vs car, 11 x truck rollover; 2 x truck vs cyclist, 1 x lost load from truck vs car, 1 x truck trailer vs car, 1 x truck vs tree, 1 x truck vs building, 1 x truck vs motorcycle, 1 x truck vs pedestrian, 1 x bus vs pedestrian; and 1 x truck vs train.

6. CRASH TYPE AND WITH RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendations arising from the coronial Inquests and Non-Inquest findings included:

1. Truck vs train:

This was a workplace incident. The heavy vehicle driver was charged with criminal offences however was found not guilty at trial. Two recommendations arose from the Non-Inquest. Both recommendations related to the locomotive crashworthiness and structural integrity of the locomotive driver's cabin. The Office of Transport Safety Regulator was involved in a parallel investigation providing information to the Coroner. WorkSafe was not involved in the investigation process.

2. A heavy articulated vehicle collided with a car:

Eight recommendations were submitted by the Coroner. These recommendations included imposing speed restrictions for the articulated vehicle, install internal speed limiters to be set at 60kph or at 80 kph if electronic stability control was fitted, driver must undertake practical and theoretical assessments, amend the articulated code of practice to include guidance on handling characteristics.

3. Truck vs car:

The heavy vehicle rolled over rounding a bend, toppling over onto a car. Recommendations included government to investigate stability control systems for heavy vehicles and for the Queensland Department of Transport to appoint a coronial officer as well as mandate the attendance of a transport inspector to the scene of fatal crashes involving heavy vehicles.

4. Truck vs. pedestrian:

This Inquest took into account five separate fatalities and recommended *the Vehicle Standards Australian Design Rules 42/04- General Safety Requirements 2005* be amended to require front warning sensors be installed during manufacture of all cab over heavy vehicles.

5. Oversized escorts Inquests:

There were two Inquests that analysed three fatal crashes. In total 12 recommendations were made. These included only granting permits for loads that are indivisible, not granting permits for loads if they can be made smaller, night-time escorts to be limited to dual carriageways and metropolitan areas, Police review the use of motorcycles as escort vehicles, oversized load activity must be well managed, the National Heavy Vehicle Regulator regard the evidence of the Inquest to develop regulations and guidelines for arrangements of oversized loads, ensuring the wording for oversized loads are more effectively communicated, public awareness campaigns ensuring public are aware of their obligations, traffic management plans must be developed and distributed to all escort parties for the escort, procedures and permit conditions to be more explicit when describing risks of transporting a wide load, using more information signs for very wide loads, more attention be given to the spacing of the escorts and the oversized load, must include this in the training for the Police officers escorting oversized loads, lighting of oversized loads to be review.

6. Unstable trailer towed by truck colliding with a vehicle:

Recommendations included Government request training providers review content of training and assessment for license holders, whether competence for loading and towing trailers should be included in the training, government consider whether medium rigid licence holders ought to be permitted to tow trailers behind medium rigid trucks, government to raise this issue with other government agencies for consideration.

7. Car struck by heavy log falling from a truck:

Coroner recommended that WorkSafe review its industry standards and guidelines to address aspects of the standards that were shown and conceded to be deficient during the Inquest.

8. Truck colliding with a push cycle:

It was recommended that Government immediately prohibit cyclists from using the highway, government engage with stakeholders to deal with safety concerns and provide an alternative route, signage should be erected on onramps to warn cyclists that the roadway was dangerous.

9. Truck vs car, double fatality:

It was recommended that government and Police maintain their awareness campaigns of the risks of using mobile phones whilst driving and ongoing attention be given to detecting those who breach the rules and consideration be given to the level of penalty applicable to such offences.

10. Truck vs tree:

It was recommended the shire conduct a risk assessment of the road with a view to placing signage at the beginning of the road to forewarn road users of the road's curves and undulations and the dangers within.

11. Truck colliding with a push cyclist:

Seven recommendations were made. Some included the routine and mandatory electronic recording of witness statements, government to regulate that vehicle stop one vehicle behind the bike box which enables drivers to see the bike. Targeted and education program to alert motorists of the risk of placing themselves immediately in front of a heavy vehicle, make such actions an offence, conventional shaped heavy vehicle should be fitted with technologies to warn drivers of obstacles and other road users in the driver's blind spot, educate all motorists about blind spots in front of a conventional heavy vehicle.

12. Bus hitting a pedestrian:

It was recommended that government urgently review the operations of the traffic and pedestrian crossings at intersections.

13. Truck vs car:

The Coroner recommended that Government proceed with the design and construction of a channelised right turn at the intersection with priority.

14. Truck vs tree:

It was recommended that the government consider enhanced education and awareness to ensure employees performing inspection of heavy vehicle are of the risks involved in not having clean components to inspect, and that government review the current memorandum of understanding between Police and Worksafe that includes a process for the notification of a heavy vehicle incident to the national heavy vehicle regulator.

15. i) Truck vs. car & ii) truck vs pedestrian:

One Inquest was held for two separate fatalities occurring at the same location. 17 recommendations were made (South Australian Government 2015). These included:

- Drivers who don't use a safety ramp when their truck is out of control face harsher punishments, up to and including jail time. Truck drivers are automatically charged with dangerous driving if they go over the speed limit of 60 kph on the downhill stretch of the freeway. Owners or companies that hire drivers pay victims and their families for accidents involving heavy vehicles. Truck drivers are required to take classes on how to drive downhill and how to use an arrester bed.
- Trainee drivers should undergo specific tuition in relation to the required manner of driving on the downhill of the South Eastern Freeway; a truck driver must be supervised when driving down the South Eastern Freeway for the first time, and the accompanying driver must have demonstrated experience and competence on that downhill; no heavy vehicle license of any kind should be issued to any person in Australia unless they have demonstrated competence in the safe negotiation of the downhill on the South Eastern Freeway.
- Speed limits for heavy vehicles are reduced to 40 km/h on the down track; improved signage, including informing drivers that heavy penalties apply if trucks and buses do not use low gear; promotion of arrester bed use; roadworthiness and maintenance be brought within the chain of responsibility regime with the *Heavy Vehicle National Law (South Australia) Act 2013* and be undertaken nationally; all heavy vehicles be subjected to a periodic and frequent inspection regime; investigating the capability of technology to detect the speed of a heavy vehicle and tell a driver that their speed is excessive and they need to use a safety ramp.
- Consider creating a zone between the Heysen Tunnels and the second arrester bed for the mandatory stopping of all heavy vehicles, with the additional requirement that if the vehicle is unable to stop in that zone, the driver must use the second safety ramp (Marcus, 2015).

However, in this Inquest the Government of the day stated it would only support 13 of the 17 recommendations (MacLennan, 2015).

16. Truck rollover:

No recommendations were made however a number of points were raised. Company did not do any act or omission to contribute to the crash. Driver not wearing seatbelt. Delays in completing investigation, investigation not completed to a required standard. Workplace incident, WorkSafe not involved.

7. FINDINGS

Over the 15-year period this study identified a total of 34 publicly available Coronial Inquest and Non-Inquest reports. In those 34 reports a total of 60 recommendations were made with five Inquests providing 43 recommendations and the remaining 29 Inquest and Non-Inquest findings providing 17 recommendations. This study supports the findings of a previous study conducted by Brodie et al. (2010) in which it was identified that Coroners recommendations from fatal crashes were infrequent. The Inquests where multiple recommendations were made came about where Coronial Inquests were combined and heard as one because the fatalities occurred at the same location or were similar types. i.e., fatal crash occurring during the escort of an oversized load.

There was one Inquest that investigated two incidents because the fatalities that occurred were the result of the same type of incident, this being a collision occurring as a result of escorting oversized loads. From these two fatalities there were seven recommendations. There was a second Inquest that also involved an oversized escort from which there were five recommendations.

There was one Inquest that had a total of eight recommendations, one Inquest had six recommendations. Twenty of the Coroners' reports focused on the heavy vehicle driver behaviours. In seven of the reports, it was noted the driver was criminally charged however the driver was found not guilty in four of the crashes. In another crash the driver pleaded guilty, despite there being evidence to suggest other contributing factors. In another crash the driver was convicted of the offences and in another crash the charges were downgraded to lesser charges to which the driver pleaded guilty.

Thirty-three of the crashes involved a workplace incident as the heavy vehicle driver was working at that time. Only one of the 33 crashes that were workplace incidents was investigated by WorkSafe.

The types and focus of recommendations made were varied. Most were directed towards the management of driver behaviour such as imposing speed restrictions, driver training, installing speed limiters in heavy vehicles, better risk management of oversized escorts, employees performing inspection of vehicles and increased penalties for drivers who do not travel at restricted speeds. There were recommendations that included increased penalties for breaching the laws, installing in-vehicle technologies such as stability control and front warning sensors and other recommendations were aimed at improving the manner in which investigations are conducted. For example, in one Inquest it was recommended that there be routine and mandatory electronic recording of interviews, another recommended the mandatory attendance of a transport inspector at the scene of a fatal crash and in another that government review its current memorandum of understanding between police and WorkSafe. Support, by way of applying a consistent investigative methodology as well as providing training to investigators on the heavy vehicle transport system, is needed. This will enable the collection of evidence and information to identify and analyse the underlying causes for targeted prevention. As stated by Brodie et al. (2009) 'Increased recognition of heavy vehicle safety beyond individual driver responsibility is needed' (p.563). In support Newnam et al. (2017) identified that a comprehensive investigative process is likely to identify interventions that have contributed to a crash all the way up to the level of regulatory bodies and Government agencies

More importantly, in 22 of the Coronial reports, it was identified that the heavy vehicle driver behaviour, actions or omissions had in some part contributed to the crash. For example, in one Inquest it was identified the driver had no experience driving a heavy vehicle and, in another Inquest, it was found the driver was significantly fatigued as a result of being under too much pressure to meet a deadline to deliver their load. However, the Inquest did not delve more deeply into the safety management system to identify 1. If the driver's employer had checked the drivers were competent and experienced to drive a heavy vehicle 2. whether the scheduling and risk management processes permitted a driver to drive a heavy vehicle to meet unrealistic deadlines causing them to become fatigued.

In addition, the role and importance of systemic investigations was recognised. In an Inquest where separate investigations had been conducted by police and the Queensland Office of Transport Safety Investigations, the Coroner noted that police were statutorily prohibited from relying on the investigation reports from another agency for prosecution purposes and that police had to independently gather and analyse the evidence using their own expertise and resources. The Coroner went on to further state that the other agency involved in the investigation was focused on identifying contributory factors for the purpose of identifying opportunities to improve safety and health (Queensland Coroners Court 2008/392 & 2008/393, p. 4).

8. DISCUSSION

8.1 Quality of crash investigations

A review of the Inquest and Non-Inquest findings suggests that systemic investigations are not being undertaken. This is supported by comments made by Coroners. This study found there were a number of comments made by Coroners regarding the quality of crash investigations. This has been consistent since 2001 where Coroners around Australia have made similar findings and expressed their concerns. For example, in a Victorian Coronial Inquest (1114/2001), the Coroner recommended that police consider developing a basic investigation standard for fatal and serious crashes. This recommendation came about due to a number of serious deficiencies identified by the Coroner of an investigation conducted by the police of a fatal crash. Additionally, the Victorian Parliament Law Reform Committee Review (2006) conducted a review of the Victorian *Coroners Act 1985* and reported that the limitations of Coroner's investigations related to transport collision had been raised in a number of forums over the previous past five years. The review identified that:

1. Coroners did not have legal control over the death investigation process nor any power to direct the investigation, and
2. There was an absence of comprehensive guidelines for Coroners conducting death investigations as well as widespread discrepancy between the standard of Coroners' investigations in Melbourne and those in rural areas.

In a Coronial Inquest regarding a vehicle colliding with an escorted oversized load, killing the car driver (Queensland Coroners Court 2199/05(0)), the family of the deceased were dissatisfied with the evidence submitted to the Coroner by the police. The family of the deceased had taken it upon themselves to assemble a substantial body of material regarding the conditions and events prior to the collision and provided that information to the Coroner. That material was subsequently forwarded by the Coroner to the police for further investigation who were then able to obtain further evidence for the Coroner. Although not criticising the investigation, the Coroner found (Queensland Coroners Court, 2199/05(0), p. 28) that a Coronial Inquest is better informed when evidence is available from all perspectives.

In another Findings of Inquest, (Queensland 2011/1631 & 2010/4091) a police officer riding a motorcycle and escorting an oversized load was struck and killed by a heavy vehicle travelling in the opposite direction. The heavy vehicle driver was charged with driving without due care and attention, however, after a three-day trial, the heavy vehicle driver was found not guilty (p. 11). In the subsequent Inquest, the deceased's wife made a submission to the Coroner to consider flaws in the way the investigation was undertaken and managed (p. 12). During the Coronial Inquest the Coroner identified a number of 'sub-optimal practices' (p.12) that included:

- Conversations with witness at the crash scene were not tape recorded.
- Detailed accounts were not taken from any witnesses on the morning of the crash.
- Police did not have witnesses adopt any notes taken of the conversations.
- Key witnesses were allowed to confer at the scene and then leave on the understanding they could attend to a Police Station at a time and place convenient to them to provide a statement.
- The defendant was spoken to by four officers on the day of the crash, but none took detailed statement or questioned the defendant closely as should have been in such circumstances.
- One officer was notionally put in charge, but other officers gave directions about aspects of the investigation without consulting with the person in charge and did not ensure the person in charge was advised of the outcomes.

- Other officers who were tasked with various inquiries or to obtain statements were inadequately briefed regarding the issues under investigation as well as the versions provided by other witnesses meaning they could contribute little to the investigation.
- The expert investigators from the Fatal Crash Unit did not arrive until two days after the crash.
- Significant delays occurred during the investigation as the supervisors allowed significant delays to occur.

The Coroner noted that 'Whilst these criticisms have some force, as a result of reviewing the investigations of numerous traffic fatalities I am aware that similar practices are common' (p. 13).

The Coroner went on to further identify a number of key points in relation to the quality of the investigation. These included the investigating police officer worked in a very busy station, the officer had very limited crash investigation training and experience, there was no specialist support, experts undertook discreet parallel investigations or reviews, there was limited coordination of the number of investigations being conducted at the same time. The Coroner noted that:

'(name redacted) was the officer in charge of a very busy division with limited crash investigation training and experience. Nonetheless, in the normal course he would investigate fatal road crashes in that division, there being at the time no specialist FCU in central region. However, in this case he was left to undertake a criminal and coronial investigation of a particularly sensitive matter, while other experts undertook discreet investigations or reviews of aspects of the incident. There was limited coordination of the four inquiries and less supervision of (name redacted).

In conclusion, the Coroner stated that '[t]he outcome was less than perfect, but probably no worse than many investigations regularly undertaken throughout the state' (p.13).

These comments raise a number of concerns at the lack of quality of investigations that are conducted of fatal crashes. The Coroner's comments suggest that sub-optimal practices in investigations are common place and the quality of heavy vehicle fatal crash investigations are not to a suitable standard.

The Coroner's comments were consistent with the findings from research conducted by the authors of this paper where a number of participants were interviewed to identify why heavy vehicle drivers were blamed for crashes. The participants in the interviews, many being either police officers or former police officers, stated that police officers, themselves included, were required to conduct heavy vehicle fatal crash investigations whilst working under strenuous circumstances, without support, in busy police stations with limited or no training or crash investigation experiences. This may, to some extent, explain the sub-standard quality of investigations being conducted resulting in deficient investigation reports being submitted to Coroners.

Research by Brodie et al. (2010) found there was no systematic approach to Coroners' investigations of heavy vehicle fatalities. The research identified that police crash expert investigators are not involved in the investigation of all fatal heavy vehicle crashes, especially those that are single heavy vehicle crashes. Generally, these investigations are conducted by general duties police often with less experience and expertise than those within the specialised crash investigation squads.

In another Non-Inquest of a single heavy vehicle rollover fatal crash killing the driver (Magistrates Court of Tasmania 2020), the Coroner found the police officer allocated to the investigation was not a qualified investigator and was attached to a police station with a very heavy workload. The Coroner concluded that it was understandable the police officer was unable to complete the investigation to a required standard and in a timely manner (Magistrates Court of Tasmania 2020, p. 7). These comments are consistent with the research findings by the authors of this paper who conducted a number of semi-structured interviews with a participant who had investigation experiences. The participants stated that

when working in busy police stations, particularly those police stations in country areas, they did not have the support or resources to properly complete a heavy vehicle fatal crash investigation, nor did they have the training, competencies or experiences to conduct those investigations.

In an Inquest finding of a fatality caused by an incorrectly loaded trailer causing it to lose balance leading to a crash, the Coroner became aware of a number of systemic failings identified during the investigation. The Coroner suggested that ‘where systemic flaws in the system are disclosed, they should be addressed with urgency and careful attention’ (Coroner’s report 2013/298913, p. 11). Later in the report, the Coroner stated in relation to the circumstance surrounding the death that:

Coroners have no professional expertise in relation to these questions. I have therefore framed the recommendations not in rigidly prescriptive terms but putting the serious issues (name redacted) death raises before the experts in the field for them to consider and resolve (p. 13).

However, the substandard quality of investigations is not just specific to police. In another example of an Inquest, the Coroner expressed concerns regarding an improperly conducted investigation by another government agency. The Coroner commented on the substandard quality of a tape-recorded interview, noting that:

The tape recording of the interview reveals a rather shambolic, rambling and unstructured interchange. The panel chair stated at the Inquest he had taken some comfort from knowing that a coronial investigation was to follow. However, subsequent events have revealed this to be illusory. While there is no doubt the panel members had high level content knowledge, it might be desirable in future to include a person with forensic expertise (Queensland Coroners Court 2009, p. 3).

The research suggests there are sub-standard and sub-optimal investigation practices that have been evident for a considerable period of time. Driscoll (2003) identified that limited investigative resources and a lack of standard investigation approaches were likely to impede the information and investigative process. Bohensky et al. (2005) identified that if the process for investigating deaths were standardised, these deaths would be more easily and efficiently investigated. Bugeja et al. (2007) concluded there were recognised limitations associated with the coronial investigations of heavy vehicle crashes and the lack of an existing systematic approach affecting investigation outcomes.

A review conducted by the Government of Western Australia Department of Treasury (2018) to improve the efficacy of coronial investigations recommended a number of efficiency and effectiveness reforms, three of which focused the lens on the quality and output of investigations. These recommendations included enhancing the powers of Coroners to obtain information outside of an Inquest, improving consistency of regional investigations and updating guidelines to police and modifying performance measures reflecting the integrated components of coronial investigations. The recommendations highlight the need for police to conduct consistent investigations.

This is not new as previous studies by Brodie et al. (2009) posited that opportunities remain through learnings from fatal crash investigations and the systematic analysis of contributing factors. In that study it was concluded that a standardised approach to heavy vehicle fatal crash investigations will support Coroners and research efforts to increase knowledge. In a subsequent study by Brodie et al. (2010) into recommendations following fatal heavy vehicle crash investigations, it was identified that investigation standards were lacking. This included a need for a minimum crash investigation standard, improved investigative practices and increased resources for data collection to enable proactive measures by investigative authorities (p. 140).

9. CONCLUSION

The analysis of the coronial Inquests and Non-Inquest findings identified that crash investigations differed in quality and complexity. This study identified there have been historical concerns raised by Coroners over the substandard quality of investigations arising from reviews and Coroners' findings. This study has revealed a number of comments from Coroners who have continued to voice their concerns of the quality of investigations and that it suggested that sub optimal practices are commonplace. The investigations were all conducted by the Police for the Coroner from differing states. The thematic analysis identified there were differing quality of investigation, some of which were criticised by the Coroner.

A review of the coronial Inquests and Non-Inquest findings revealed that there did not appear to be a standardised approach to the investigations. There were varying degrees of quality and detail as evidenced by Coroners' remarks and the investigations did not identify contributory factors across the levels of the socio-technical system. Most factors identified in the coronial Inquests would more than likely be limited in scope because the investigations did not appear to adopt a systematic approach. It is also highly likely that other systems factors at the upper levels of the socio-technical system were present however not identified nor investigated due to the investigator's lack of understanding and knowledge of effective investigation practices.

REFERENCES

- Bohensky, M., Ibrahim, J.E., O'Brien, A.L., Emmett, S.L., Newman, E., Charles, A., & Young, C. (2005). World without borders. Integrating clinical perspectives into coronial jurisdiction in Victoria, Australia. *Journal of Medicine and Law*, 25(1), 13-29.
- Brodie, L., Bugeja, L., & Ibrahim, J.E. (2009). Heavy vehicle driver fatalities: Learnings from fatal road crash investigations in Victoria. *Journal of Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 41, 557-564. DOI: 10.1016/j.aap.2009.02.005.
- Brodie, L., Bugeja, L., & Ibrahim, J.E. (2010). Coroner's recommendations following fatal heavy vehicle crash investigations. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health*, 34(2), 136-141. DOI: 10.1111/j.1753-6405.2010.00497.x.
- Bugeja, L., Symmons, M., Brodie, L., Osborne, N., & Ibrahim, J.E. (2007). *Development of a specialist investigation standard for heavy vehicle fatal collisions in Victoria*. In P. Schofield (Ed.): *Conference Proceedings of the 2007 Australasian Road Safety Research, Policing and Education Conference*. Melbourne Victoria Australia: The Meeting Planners, 1-10.
- Bugeja, L., Ibrahim, J.E., Ozanne-Smith, J., Brodie, L.R., & McClure, R.J. (2012). Application of a public health framework to examine the characteristics of coroner's recommendations for injury prevention. *Journal of Injury Prevention*, 18, 326-333. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/injuryprev-2011-040146>
- Burns, B. (2014). Lessons learned from the Coroner's court. *Kai Tiaki Nursing New Zealand*, 20(8), 21-23.
- Cikara, I., Dell, G., Toft, Y., Dell, S., & Skrizovska, M. (2020). The need for enhanced heavy vehicle crash investigations: Beyond 'blame the driver'. *Transactions of the VSB - Technical University of Ostrava, Safety Engineering Series*, 15(1), 60-72, (ISSN: 1805-3238). DOI: 10.35182/tses-2020-0007.
- Dell, G. (2015). Foreword, in Viner D, *Occupational risk control: Predicting and preventing the unwanted*. Gower Publishing, Farnham.
- Dell, G. (2019). *The lessons from 15 years of airline corporate governance roles (and 40 years of air safety investigations)*. Presentation at the Australia and New Zealand Societies of Air Safety Investigation, Wellington, New Zealand.

- Doecke, S., Thompson, J., & Stokes, C. (2020). How do we prevent and mitigate crashes? Evidence from Australian at-scene in-depth crash investigations. *Journal of Safety Research*, 1(2), 35- 43.
- Driscoll, T. (2003). Traumatic work-related deaths and Australian Coroners. A thesis for preventions. *The Journal of the Australasian Coroners Society Inc*, Issue 2.
- Fogliani, R. (2017). *Office of the state Coroner for Western Australia. Annual Report 2016-2017*. https://www.coronerscourt.wa.gov.au/_files/Annual_Report_2016_17.pdf
- Government of Western Australia, Department of Treasury. (2018). Improving the efficiency of coronial investigations, 90 day regulatory mapping and reform project series report no 4.
- Heavy Vehicle National Law (South Australia) Act 2012*.
- Klockner, K., & Toft, Y. (2014). *Accident modelling using social network analysis for complex socio technical systems*. Australian Safety System Conference (ASSC 2014), Melbourne, Victoria, Australia.
- Marcus, C. (2015). *Coroner recommends national training for truck drivers on the South Eastern Freeway into Adelaide*. ABC News [online]. https://www.abc.net.au/news/2015-01-12/Coroner_recommends_national_training_for_truck_drivers_on_the_South_Eastern_Freeway/6012304. [Accessed 23 June 2021].
- MacLennan, L. (2015). *Truck drivers could be jailed if low gear not used on South Eastern Freeway decent in Adelaide Hills. Truck drivers who fail to engage low gear when descending the South Eastern Freeway in the Adelaide Hills could be jailed under legislation the South Australian Government is drafting*, Sydney.
- Magistrates Court of Tasmanian. (28 October 2020). *Record of investigation into death (without Inquest), James William Espie*.
- Productivity Commission. (2020). *National Transport Regulatory Reform, Inquiry report: Overview and recommendations*. Australian Government, report no. 94, Canberra. ISSN 1447-1329-1447-1337.
- Newnam, S., Goode, N., Salmon, P., & Stevenson, M. (2017). 'Reforming the road freight transportation system using systems thinking: An investigation of coronial Inquests in Australia. *Journal of Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 101, 28-36. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org.exypoxy.lib.monash.edu.au/10.1016/j.aap.2017.01.016>
- Queensland Courts, Office of the State Coroner. (22 December 2008). Findings of Inquest, Innisfail Coroners Court, file number 2199/05(0).
- Queensland Court, Office of the State Coroner. (23 December 2009). Findings of Inquest, Brisbane Coroners Court, file number COR868-870/06.
- Queensland Courts, Office of the State Coroner. (15 March 2013). Findings of Inquest, Brisbane Coroners Court, file number 2011/1631 & 2010/4091.
- Queensland Courts, Office of the State Coroner (5 June 2014). Findings of Inquest, Toowoomba Coroners Court, file number 2012/334.
- Queensland Courts, Office of the State Coroner. (27 March 2018). Findings of Inquest, Toowoomba Coroners Court, file number 2014/3137.
- Queensland Coroners Court, Office of the State Coroner, Findings of Investigation: Non-Inquest findings into the deaths of Michael Smithers and Richard Wetherell, 2008/392 & 2008/393, Cairns, Australia.
- Selk, S., & Benner, L. (2019). Accident investigation challenges for process safety practitioners. *Journal of Process Safety Progress*, 28(4), 1-9.
- South Australian Government. (2015). Response to the deputy State Coroner's recommendations of January 2015, following the death of Mr James William Venning on the South Eastern Freeway, September 2015.
- State Coroners Court. (13 June 2016). New South Wales, Findings from Inquest, 2013/298913.
- Studdert, D.M., & Cordner, S.M. (2010). Impact of coronial investigations on manner and cause of death determinations in Australia, 2000 – 2007. *Medical Journal of Australia*, 192(8), 444-447. DOI:10.5694/j.1326-5377.2010.tb03582.x

The Coroners Act 1985 (Victoria).

Vehicle Standards Australian Design Rules 42/04- General Safety Requirements 2005.

Victorian Coroners Court. (2001). Case number 1114/2001.

Victorian Parliament Law Reform Committee. (2006). *Inquiry into the review of the Coroners Act 1985.* Parliamentary Paper No. 229 of Session 2003-06. ISBN-0-9757984-1-3, Melbourne Victoria.

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